

**AN EFFECTIVE VERSION OF A THEOREM OF SHIODA ON THE
RANKS OF ELLIPTIC CURVES GIVEN BY $y^2 = f(x) + m^2$**

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Abstract

In this short note, we extend results in several papers by proving effectively that for m sufficiently large, an elliptic curve given by $y^2 = f(x) + m^2$, with $f(x)$ a cubic polynomial that splits over \mathbb{Z} , has rank at least 2. This also constitutes an effective version of a theorem of Shioda.

1. Introduction

In a well known paper on a family of elliptic curves, Brown and Myers [3] prove that the rank of any elliptic curve of the form

$$y^2 = x^3 - x + m^2, \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}$$

is always at least 2 for $m \geq 2$. Since then, a number of other papers have been written on families of curves extending the result of Brown and Myers. These include the work of Antoniewicz [1] on curves of the form $y^2 = x^3 - m^2x + 1$, Tadić [10] on curves of the form $y^2 = x^3 - x + m^2$, Fujita and Nara [4] and Juyal and Kumar [6] on curves of the form $y^2 = x^3 - m^2x + n^2$, and most recently, Hatley and Stack [5] on curves of the form $y^2 = x^3 - x + m^6$.

In this article, we consider the slightly more general family of curves given by

$$E_{f,m} : y^2 = f(x) + m^2, \tag{1.1}$$

in which $f(x)$ is a cubic polynomial with three distinct integer roots a, b, c , and $m \geq 0$ is an integer. Our goal is to prove that the rank of $E_{f,m}$ is similarly bounded from below because of the existence of independent points on the curve provided that m is large enough with respect to a, b and c . In fact, it is not difficult to construct examples with relatively small m for which the result is false. For example, Voutier [11] has found that the families of curves $y^2 = x(x-a)(x-b) + m^2$, with $(a, b, m) = (1, 4k^2, 4k^3 - 4k)$ and $(a, b, m) = (3, 8k^2 + 6, 8k^3 + 6k)$, are very often curves of rank 1.

Proving a lower bound for the rank as discussed above was the topic of an earlier version of our work prior to learning of the much earlier work of Shioda in [7], wherein he proves a lower bound of 2 for the rank of

$$E_f(t) : y^2 = f(x) + t^2$$

regarded as an elliptic surface. Applying Silverman’s Specialization Theorem in [8] to Shioda’s result is already enough to effectively prove the result we present here. However, we feel the methods used here are somewhat more natural, using a combination of group theoretic and Diophantine methods, and provide perhaps more hope of getting a bound for m which is closer to the truth. Indeed, we are unable to find any curve of the form (1.1) of rank 1 for which $m \geq \max(|a|, |b|, |c|)^2$.

We first remark that if the curve in question is given by

$$y^2 = (x - a)(x - b)(x - c) + m^2,$$

and we let $X = x - c$, then the curve can be rewritten as

$$y^2 = X(X + c - a)(X + c - b) + m^2,$$

and so there is no loss in generality by restricting our focus to the case that $f(x)$ has a root at $x = 0$, i.e., that $c = 0$. However, we will state our result in full generality.

We now state the main result of this paper.

Theorem 1. *Let a, b, c be distinct integers. Then there is a computable constant $C = C(a, b, c)$, depending on a, b, c , with the property that if $m > C$, then the rank of the curve*

$$y^2 = (x - a)(x - b)(x - c) + m^2 \tag{1.2}$$

is at least 2.

We fall short of proving an effective result on the torsion subgroup. In particular, it appears that for fixed a, b, c , the torsion subgroup is trivial for m sufficiently large, however we are unable to effectively deal with the possibility that it has order 5. In fact, a much stronger property appears to hold; if $\phi_5(x)$ denotes the fifth division polynomial of the curve in (1.2), our computations show that this polynomial is actually irreducible for all m sufficiently large.

2. An Independence Criterion

In this section we prove a simple result which will provide our overall strategy to prove Theorem 1.1.

Lemma 1. *Assume that $E(\mathbb{Q})$ is 2-torsion free. If P and Q are points of infinite order such that all three of $P, Q, P + Q$ are not in $2E(\mathbb{Q})$, then P and Q are independent.*

Proof. The order of the torsion subgroup T is odd by hypothesis, which by Mazur’s theorem, implies that it is one of 3, 5, or 7. Let p denote this order, and notice that for any $P \in T$, $P = 2 * ((p+1)/2) * P$, so that $P \in 2E(\mathbb{Q})$. It is well-known that if for an arbitrary rational torsion point T , any linear combination of P, Q, T (except for T alone) is not in $2E(\mathbb{Q})$, then P and Q are independent. The assertion now immediately follows from the observation above that $T \in 2E(\mathbb{Q})$ for any rational torsion point T of odd order. \square

3. Proof of Theorem 1.1

Proof. We now turn our attention to the proof of Theorem 1.1. By Lemma 2.1, it is enough to prove that if m is large enough, then E has no rational 2-torsion; (a, m) and (b, m) are not points of order 3, 5 or 7; $(a, m), (b, m)$ and $(a, m) + (b, m)$ (which equals $(0, -m)$) are not in $2E(\mathbb{Q})$.

In order to achieve these, it becomes significantly simpler to deal with a short Weierstrass equation, and a short computation shows that the curve in (1.1), with $c = 0$ (as remarked just prior to the statement of Theorem 1.1), can be written in the form

$$Y^2 = X^3 + AX + B, \tag{3.1}$$

where $A = -27(a^2 - ab + b^2)$ and $B = (27m)^2 + 3A(a + b) + 27(a + b)^3$.

We begin by considering the problem of eliminating 2-torsion. If (r, s) denotes a 2-torsion point on the curve given in (3.1), then $s = 0$ and r is an integer root of the cubic therein. This implies that there is an integer t for which

$$X^3 + AX + B = (X - r)(X^2 + rX + t).$$

Therefore, $A = t - r^2$ and $B = -rt$, and by substituting $t = r^2 + A$ into $B = -rt$, we see that $B = -r^3 - Ar$. Using the expression above for B shows that

$$(27m)^2 = (-r)^3 + A(-r) - 3A(a + b) - 27(a + b)^3.$$

Therefore, the pair $(-r, 27m)$ is an integral point on the curve

$$y^2 = x^3 + Ax - (3A(a + b) + 27(a + b)^3).$$

By the main result in [2], it follows that $m \leq C_1(a, b)$.

The next step is to show that for m large, both (a, m) and (b, m) are not points of order 3, 5 or 7. This is achieved by computing the division polynomials of the

curve defined by (3.1), and evaluating at $x = a$ and $x = b$. This was achieved using MAGMA's *Evaluate* function, and not surprisingly, the resulting values were found not to be identically zero. The division polynomials were of the form $F_{a,b}(x, m)$, and thus m is bounded in terms of a and b by the height of F after making the substitution $x = a$ and $x = b$ respectively. As one would expect, the largest height arose from the 7-th division polynomial, which we do not display here. If we let $C_2(a, b)$ denote this height, then for $m \geq \max(C_1(a, b), C_2(a, b))$, we deduce that both (a, m) and (b, m) are points of infinite order.

To complete the proof of Theorem 2.1, we will show that for m large enough, none of (a, m) , (b, m) or $(0, -m)$ are in $2E$. We will describe the case for $(0, -m)$, as the other two cases give similar bounds. We will use the doubling formula from p.58-59 of [9], which allows us to use the equation $y^2 = x(x - a)(x - b) + m^2$ for our curve. In this case, the basic quantities from [9] are

$$a_1 = a_3 = 0, a_2 = -(a + b), a_4 = ab, a_6 = m^2,$$

from which we deduce that

$$\lambda = \frac{3x^2 - 2(a + b)x + ab}{2y}, \nu = \frac{-x^3 + abx + 2m^2}{2y},$$

from which it follows that $0 = \lambda^2 + (a + b) - 2x$ and $-m = -\lambda \cdot 0 - \nu = -\nu$. The two expressions for ν combine to give the equation

$$x^4 - 2abx^2 - 8m^2x + (a^2b^2 + 4m^2(a + b)) = 0.$$

This equation in x and m satisfies the condition of Runge's theorem on Diophantine equations (see [12]), giving an upper bound $C_3(a, b)$ for m . □

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